

THE USAGE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE PLATFORMS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Ismatova Mekhribon¹

4- year student of

Ulasheva Shakhlo²

Research supervisor:

Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi Karshi branch

¹⁻²Tashkent University of Information

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Abstract: This article talks about the usage of modern innovative platforms in teaching foreign languages. Based on scientific data, the author analyzed the problem on the basis of existing literature and studied the specific aspects of the role of innovative technologies.

Keywords: Foreign languages, innovative technology, media, internet, international.

Today, the main focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of educational activities students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

Popular methods of teaching and learning English, Internet resources were used in the research process. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical-deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualization of teaching taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning and ensures differentiation. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary;

practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical events.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information they need: regional geographical materials, news in the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

A number of didactic problems can be solved using the Internet in English in lessons: formation of reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work aims to explore the possibilities of Internet technologies to expand the horizons of schoolchildren, establish and maintain business relations and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries. Students can take part in online tests, quizzes, contests, Olympiads, correspond with their peers in other countries, chat, videoconference, etc.

Students can learn about the problem they are currently working on in a project. The meaningful basis of mass computerization is related to the fact that the modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the conditions of mental work, in general, in any of its forms. The computer has one characteristic that defines its use as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in the acquisition of knowledge, and that is its inanimate nature. The machine can have a "friendly" relationship with the user and sometimes "support" him, but he will never show signs of anger and will not let you feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are implemented in the process of realizing this main goal. Communicative approach includes communication training and the formation of intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet has no meaning - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the number and size of the participants in it. the biggest conversation on. Attending a foreign language class for him, we create a real communication model.

Currently, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanitarianism of education are given priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The

ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach a free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond to different situations, i.e. contact Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to correct this error. Communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows distinguishing this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is highly encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts by means of speech." By teaching the real language, the Internet helps to build speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to give appropriate answers to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered education is the project method as a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprojects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate

instills moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, builds creativity and activates students. In general, the inseparability of teaching and education is observed in the process of teaching the project.

The project method develops students' communication skills, communication culture, the ability to form ideas concisely and easily, tolerance of the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from various sources, modern processes using computer technologies, creates a language environment that contributes to the emergence of a natural need. in foreign language communication.

The project form of work is one of the most relevant technologies that allow students to apply the accumulated knowledge on the subject. Students expand their horizons, the limits of knowledge of the language, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, and thus create the possibility of direct contact with the real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom only with the help of textbooks.

Working on a project is a creative process. The student searches for a solution to the problem independently or under the guidance of the teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills.

In the course of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the program materials of almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities.

TO modern technologies cooperation technology is also applicable. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in different educational conditions. Children are united in groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, while everyone's role is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. Therefore, weak students try to find out what they do not understand from weak ones, and strong students try to make the weak ones understand the task thoroughly. And the whole class benefits because the gaps are closed together.

The introduction of information technologies into education will greatly diversify the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to the computer, the Internet and multimedia, a unique opportunity was created for students to absorb a large amount of information with further analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also expanding

significantly. In the context of using multimedia, students get information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and conduct teleconferences.

The main criteria for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in language portfolio technology is the test. The priority of this technology is to direct the educational process from the teacher to the student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his educational activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills to learn information independently. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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